

Gully erosion potential by hypsometric curve and morphometric analysis

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Abstract— The formation and development of gullies is a highly intensive process of soil erosion that is often overlooked in river basin policies and strategies. Despite the worldwide spread of the phenomenon, our ability to assess and simulate gullying and its impacts remains limited. Our study shows how an exclusively morphometric approach, based on the construction of the hypsometric curve and applied to small catchments that are lithologically homogeneous, is able to predict the triggering height of gullies and the energy (in terms of "energy efficiency" along the hypsographic curve) required for their activation; these two points are found to coincide.

I. INTRODUCTION

The formation and development of gullies is a very intensive soil erosion process that is often overlooked in river basin policies and strategies and is responsible for more than 90% of the sediment load in streams [1-5].

Despite the worldwide distribution of the phenomenon, some particular aspects of these processes have been little studied, i.e. the development of reliable models for their formation and evolution. The latter is mainly due to the diversity of geomorphological features and processes involved [6-8].

The present study, based on studies already begun by the authors on this topic [9], allows us to mark, with an original morphometric approach and simple tools implemented in a GIS environment, the transition between the sectors of the basin characterized by the different erosive capacity of running waters, confirming the intuition of Strahler [10, 11] that the inflection point of the hypsometric curve would have a significant geomorphological value; furthermore, it shows that the height of

the gully heads and the potential energy required for their activation can be related to the mean elevation of the basin.

II. DATA AND METHODS

We tested our approach on 35 sample basins in three test areas: one in central Italy, another in the Mountain States (U.S.A.-Wyoming) and a third in New Zealand (Fig.1). These basins are characterized by different climatic, morphometric, geomorphological and land-use conditions, as well as different degrees of anthropization. The only similarities are the less permeable bedrock, which allows the formation of a well-developed hydrographic network, and the low degree of tectonic conditioning.

The study has been organized in several steps:

- Calculation of the basic morphometric parameters with the aid of GIS procedures using DTMs with a resolution of 10 m, which can be downloaded free of charge from the links <https://doi.org/10.13127/tinitaly/1>, <https://portal.opentopography.org/> and <https://maps.gns.cri.nz/> for the Italian, US and New Zealand catchments respectively.
- Construction of the hypsometric curve;
- Analytical determination of the energy potential of running waters within the river catchment area
- Detection of gully heads by satellite image interpretation and verification of the proposed model;
- Calculation of Şen's "energy index" [12] for gully head formation.

Figure 1. Location map of the study areas with indication of the catchments analyzed (red polygons)

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In a first step, we carried out the morphometric analysis of the 35 basins using the DTMs described above with a resolution of 10 m (Fig.2a). To estimate the mean elevation of each catchment, we constructed the hypsometric curve, which represents the fraction of the area of a catchment above a given elevation. The curves obtained are presented in non-dimensional form (i.e. plots of the relative height (h/H) against the relative area (a/A) of the studied region), which allows comparison between different hydrographic catchments. For the specific objectives of this work and to make the correlations between the relative elevations of the analyzed basins clearer, we created the hypsometric curve in a semi-dimensional form with the "normalized" basin area values (a/A between 0 and 1, Fig.2b).

Figure 2. a) GIS elaboration from a DTM with a resolution of 10 m; b) Example of a hypsometric curve with indication of the value and position of the relative Oblique Inflection Points (OIPs). Modified after [9]

The equation of the hypsometric curve, which is expressed with a 3rd degree polynomial function, shows two special points (Oblique Inflection Points - OIPs), one of which corresponds to the change in curve slope in the upper part of the basin and the other lies outside the diagram area. In real-world applications where a system is modeled using a curve, finding the inflection point is crucial to predict the behavior of the system. In the specific case of a hydrographic basin, Strahler [10] has emphasized that this change in concavity (corresponding to the "higher" point) marks the point [...at which the rate of decrease of mass upwards changes from an increasingly rapid rate of decline to a diminishing rate of decline]; in other words, this point represents the transition from a region of greater to a region of lower energy on the slope. As far as the determination of the energy potential within a watershed is concerned, it can be shown that the power of a water particle moving without friction and descending by a value dh can be expressed in the form

$$P = (mg \sin \alpha) \sqrt{2gh} \quad (1)$$

with P expressed in watt (Joule/sec).

This formula tells us that in the hypsometric curve for $h=0$ the power $P=0$ and that for $h=1$ P is equal to $(mg \sin \alpha) \sqrt{2g}$. Of course, this is an "ideal" system that does not take into account the energy dissipated by friction, but in absolute terms it can be compared with the morphometric evaluations.

Figure 3. a) An example of a catchment in New Zealand showing the relationship between gully heads and the mean elevation of the basin (light blue polyline). b) The same catchment with a comparison between potential energy and mean elevation of the basin

As can be seen from the example in Fig. 3a (referring to a sample basin in New Zealand), the gully heads are generally in line with the contour line corresponding to the mean elevation of the basin (calculated from the hypsometric curve); this height is practically identical to that of the inflection point (between the two calculated along the same hypsometric curve), which is at a higher elevation (Table 1). The gully heads are also located at an altitude corresponding to the relative maximum of energy that runs from the watershed downward (Fig.3b).

Although the calculated energy value is significant, it cannot be directly linked to the relationships between relative height and area (hypsometric curve) in a drainage basin.

To overcome this problem, an approach similar to that used in literature to measure the hydroelectric potential in a catchment was used (single point method, [12]). The single point method relates the "hydropower" P to the specific density of the water γ , the flow rate Q and the falling head H .

$$P = \gamma Q H \tag{2}$$

It can be shown that if, starting from equation (2), we write the differences in terms of power gain dP , height dH and flow rate dQ and use the well-known formula of the Rational method $Q = C I A$ to determine the flow rate (where C corresponds to the runoff coefficient, which varies between 0 and 1, I is the rainfall intensity and A is the basin area), we obtain the following relationship

$$dP = \gamma C i (dH)(dA) \tag{3}$$

If we consider the density of the water equal to 1, the runoff coefficient equal to 1 (only the drainage area and the altitude are taken into account without geological influences) and the rainfall intensity also equal to 1 (i.e. the drainage basin, which is effective in the whole area, can be adjusted according to the rainfall intensity), we can write

$$dP = (dH)(dA) \tag{4}$$

The product of the infinitesimal increase in drainage area and the decrease in height is defined as the "energy index" (E_i) of the catchment [12], in which hydrometeorological and geological effects do not play any role. In practice, E_i can be defined as the infinitesimal energy per unit density of a catchment subject to a constant precipitation intensity and a uniform runoff coefficient.

Based on these assumptions, it is possible to fit (4) to the hypsographic curve of the catchment as follows:

$$E_i = h/H * a/A \tag{5}$$

Once the E_i values have been calculated for a given number of pairs of h/H and a/A values along the hypsometric curve, it is possible to choose the value associated with the mean elevation of the selected basin (Fig. 4a); the summary of the results for all 35 basins analyzed can be found in Table 1.

Looking at the values obtained, it is noticeable that the average value of E_i is 0.24, with a small standard deviation (0.05). If we want to calculate the interquartile range (IQR), which measures the dispersion of the central values of the data set (difference between the third quartile Q_3 and the first quartile Q_1), we obtain a value of 0.045, which represents the values between 0.21 and 0.26. The mean value of 0.24 obtained is compatible with the efficiency classes of energy potential for hydropower generation proposed by Şen [12], which considers the interval of E_i between 0.3 and 0.6 as "normal".

Figure 4. a) Energy hypsometric index calculated for the sample catchment; b) frequency distribution of the E_i values for all the basins analyzed

TABLE I. SUMMARY TABLE WITH ALL THE RESULTS OF THE PROCESSING DESCRIBED IN THE TEXT. STANDARD DEVIATION σ REFERS TO COLUMNS 2, 4 AND 5

BASIN	OIP (m)	Hypso Int	Hmean gullies Field (m)	Hmean (m)	Ei	Std. Dev. σ
Basin 1 ITALY	230.16	0.431	230.50	227.35	0.23	1.41
Basin 2 ITALY	181.40	0.473	196.50	184.90	0.23	6.45
Basin 3 ITALY	192.07	0.483	195.91	202.04	0.24	4.11
Basin 4 ITALY	165.45	0.459	177.20	166.69	0.22	5.27
Basin 5 ITALY	151.46	0.401	169.12	162.08	0.19	7.26
Basin 6 ITALY	300.18	0.487	305.15	287.85	0.25	7.27
Basin 7 ITALY	227.69	0.402	239.11	236.99	0.19	4.96
Basin 8 ITALY	180.31	0.355	196.15	198.23	0.16	8.00
Basin 9 ITALY	201.14	0.378	245.30	229.78	0.18	18.29
Basin 10 ITALY	173.46	0.417	185.40	177.92	0.20	4.93
Basin 11 ITALY	288.55	0.472	284.64	295.61	0.23	4.54
Basin 12 ITALY	222.57	0.439	193.81	229.48	0.21	15.45
Basin 13 ITALY	230.34	0.461	244.94	231.95	0.23	6.54
Basin 14 ITALY	174.71	0.376	171.35	182.83	0.17	4.82
Basin 1 USA	1482.57	0.529	1485.21	1474.72	0.29	4.46
Basin 2 USA	1504.98	0.559	1512.44	1502.05	0.28	4.37
Basin 3 USA	1447.48	0.481	1453.69	1445.21	0.24	3.58
Basin 4 USA	1514.94	0.443	1523.71	1516.26	0.21	3.86
Basin 5 USA	1532.76	0.465	1544.26	1535.71	0.22	4.88

Basin 6 USA	1454.10	0.530	1449.98	1451.71	0.27	1.69
Basin 7 USA	1450.01	0.598	1452.55	1445.61	0.31	2.87
Basin 8 USA	1401.72	0.472	1400.84	1395.11	0.25	2.93
Basin 9 USA	1427.15	0.601	1419.11	1411.31	0.33	6.47
Basin 10 USA	1501.15	0.506	1511.69	1501.36	0.24	4.92
Basin 11 USA	1502.48	0.526	1504.36	1498.66	0.27	2.37
Basin 1 NZ	395.41	0.315	418.77	426.09	0.11	13.08
Basin 2 NZ	337.64	0.442	340.16	341.92	0.22	1.76
Basin 3 NZ	326.47	0.643	329.12	303.81	0.42	11.36
Basin 4 NZ	261.54	0.419	255.65	259.25	0.26	2.42
Basin 5 NZ	353.23	0.487	348.29	342.02	0.27	4.59
Basin 6 NZ	466.11	0.428	474.32	469.60	0.23	3.36
Basin 7 NZ	324.75	0.472	325.15	321.07	0.25	1.84
Basin 8 NZ	316.10	0.423	332.28	328.15	0.22	6.86
Basin 9 NZ	328.34	0.465	331.88	334.28	0.21	2.44
Basin 10 NZ	294.08	0.366	298.39	294.34	0.21	1.97

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work shows that morphometric analysis, and in particular the use of the hypsometric curve, is an extremely valid tool for a qualitative-quantitative assessment of erosion processes in a hydrographic basin. The analysis of 35 sample basins, which are essentially homogeneous from a lithological point of view, has shown that the trigger altitude of the deepening processes (gullies) essentially coincides with the mean elevation of the basin and with the height in the hypsometric curve corresponding to their inflection point; this height corresponds, among other things, to the relative maximum of the energy flowing downwards from the watershed.

Finally, the study defines an "energy index" E_i that is compatible with the efficiency classes of energy potential proposed in literature for hydropower generation.

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